

**Sama Radial Indicator (SRI) and 3-D Digital Maturity Model
(3DDMM) for Measuring Digital Maturity of Organizations in the H&T
Industry of Sri Lanka**

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation changes the horizons of the Hospitality and Tourism (H&T) industry. More than ever, tourists have the opportunity to access real-time information about accommodations, travel, and other travel-related details; hence, they have become more demanding regarding prices and facilities. To survive in the highly competitive market, the organizations in the H&T industry are forced to adopt digital technologies. However, digitalization is a time-consuming and costly process, hence, organizations need to assess their place in the digitalization journey. Digital Maturity (DM) is the measurement used to determine the degree of adoption of digital technologies. This study is focused on assessing the DM of organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka, a famous travel destination. The population of the study was the ‘Accommodation Sector’ of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka. A random sample of one hundred organizations was selected for the data collection, a structured questionnaire was used to obtain the data from employers/ employees of the organizations. This study used the recently developed 3-D Digital Maturity Model (3DDMM) for measuring the DM of the organizations. The 3DDMM defines its dimensions: Digital Capability (DC) of organization, Leadership Capability (LC) of organization, and Digital Literacy of employers/employees (DL_E) as continuous random variables, but as per the literature, they are qualitative random variables that are not directly measurable. The Sama Radial Indicator (SRI) is a recently developed measurement scale that is said to be capable of converting a qualitative random variable to a continuous scale, hence, this study used SRI to measure the variables.

Results of the study revealed that variables DC, LC, and DL_E are continuous random variables, further satisfy the normality criterion. Then the study used 3DDMM to calculate the DM of organizations. It was found that the DC and LC of the organizations of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka are moderate, whilst the DL_E is high. The DM of the organizations is also high and follows a Chi distribution. It is concluded that SRI is a suitable scale for converting qualitative random variables to a continuous scale, and 3DDMM is a suitable model for measuring the DM of organizations.

Keywords: Digital Maturity, Sama Radial Indicator, 3D-Digital Maturity Model

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The Hospitality and Tourism industry (H&T) is a vast sector that facilitates socio-economic development worldwide. The H&T industry is undergoing a significant transformation driven by digital technologies (Buhalis & Law, 2008). Innovations in artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, the Internet of Things (IoT), and mobile technologies are reshaping how services are delivered, how businesses operate, and how consumers engage with travel and hospitality brands. This Digital Transformation (DT) is enhancing customer experience and improving operational efficiency, marketing strategies, and revenue management. DT has revolutionized customer engagement in the H&T. Mobile apps, virtual assistants, and AI-powered chatbots allow for seamless booking experiences and customer service. Personalization through big data enables tailored travel recommendations, dynamic pricing, and customized services based on user preferences and behavior. Smart technologies such as IoT devices and automation systems have led to more efficient operations in hotels and travel companies. Smart rooms with automated lighting, temperature control, and digital concierge services reduce operational costs and enhance guest comfort. The integration of big data analytics allows businesses to forecast demand, manage inventory, and optimize pricing strategies. Real-time data from online bookings, customer feedback, and social media provides valuable insights for better decision-making (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). Social media platforms, influencer marketing, and user-generated content have become crucial for promoting destinations and hospitality services. Augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) are also being used to offer virtual tours of destinations and hotels, enhancing pre-purchase decision-making (Khanal, 2024). As technology continues to evolve, businesses that adapt strategically will gain a competitive edge in this dynamic landscape. While DT brings numerous benefits, challenges such as cybersecurity threats, the digital divide, data privacy concerns, and the need for workforce reskilling also arise. Smaller enterprises may also struggle to keep up with rapid technological changes due to limited resources.

1.2 H&T Industry of Sri Lanka under the Digital Transformation

Sri Lanka's tourism industry is a critical pillar of its economy, known for its diverse cultural heritage, natural beauty, and biodiversity. In recent years, digital transformation has emerged as a key enabler for the growth and resilience of the tourism sector. Through the adoption of digital technologies, Sri Lanka is working toward enhancing tourist experiences, streamlining operations, and promoting the country more effectively in global markets. Digital platforms have become the primary medium for promoting Sri Lanka as a travel destination. The Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority (SLTDA) and Sri Lanka Tourism Promotion Bureau (SLTPB) have invested in digital campaigns, search engine marketing, and social media to reach global audiences (SLTPB, 2022). Many tourism service providers in Sri Lanka, including hotels, tour operators, and transportation services, have adopted online booking systems, enabling tourists to plan their trips digitally. Platforms like Booking.com and Airbnb also support local tourism entrepreneurs. However, digital penetration among small and medium tourism businesses (SMEs) remains uneven. Many operators still rely on traditional methods due to limited digital literacy or infrastructure.

1.3 Research Problem

Sri Lanka has been a famous travel destination over the past centuries. Digital transformation presents a powerful opportunity for Sri Lanka to revive and modernize its H&T industry. However, the H&T industry of Sri Lanka may have many challenges in digitalization. The H&T industry of the country comprises many small organizations (SLTDA, 2023). Many small business owners and employees in tourism may lack of training in digital tools; Rural areas, where many tourism assets are located, have limited internet and IT infrastructure (Konarasinghe, 2013). DT is a time-consuming and costly process; hence, organizations are urged to see how mature they are in digital transformation. Digital maturity (DM) is the measurement used to assess the degree of adoption and application of digital technologies incorporated into business models (Rossmann, 2018). It was hard to find studies measuring the DM of organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka.

As per the literature, the DM of an organization is measured by its digital capabilities and leadership capabilities (Westerman, Bonnet & McAfee, 2014). However, recent studies have shown that DM depends on the digital literacy of organizations as well (Uchhira, 2021; Rohn 2022). In order to fill the knowledge gap, Konarasinghe (2025) has developed a model, named the 3-D Digital Maturity Model (3DDMM), to measure the DM of an organization. The model uses three dimensions: Digital Capabilities (DC), Leadership Capabilities (LC), and Digital Literacy of employers/employees (DL_E) of the organization, to measure the DM. However, the model has not yet been empirically tested. Hence, it is necessary to test the 3DDMM with real-life data.

The variables: DC, LC, and DL_E are qualitative random variables measured through Latent variables (Konarasinghe, 2025). In general, LVs are measured by multi-item scales, such as the Likert scale (Rossmann, 2018). However, Konarasinghe (2025)

defined DC, LC, and DL_E as real-valued continuous random variables. Hence, it is necessary to convert these qualitative random variables into a continuous scale.

Literature reveals that the Sama Radial Indicator (SRI) of Konarasinghe (2023) can convert qualitative random variables into a continuous scale; furthermore, it is stated that the variables measured through SRI are normally distributed. Normality of random variables is an essential criterion for many statistical analyses; hence, SRI would be filling the existing knowledge gap. Yet, the indicator SRI has not been practically used for measuring qualitative random variables

Based on the above, the following research questions were identified

Research Questions

- RQ1: Are variables measured through SRI continuous and normally distributed?
- RQ2: What is the behaviour of DC, LC, and DL of the employers/ employees of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka?
- RQ3: Is 3DDMM capable of measuring the DM of organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka?

1.4 Objectives of the study

- I. To measure the latent variables using the SRI and test whether the variables are continuous and normally distributed.
- II. To find the behaviour of DC, LC, and DL of the employers/employees of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka.
- III. To test the ability of 3DDMM for measuring the DM of organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Measuring digital maturity refers to assessing how well an organization or industry has adopted and integrated digital technologies into its operations, strategy, culture, and customer experience (Westerman et. al. 2014). It is a critical process for understanding current capabilities and guiding future digital transformation efforts. Digital maturity assessments help organizations identify where they are on the digital transformation journey. It provides a clear starting point and helps develop a tailored roadmap for future digital investments and initiatives. For example, an organization assessing its digital maturity might discover a lack of data analytics capability and plan to invest in data infrastructure over the next years.

Digital maturity assessments allow benchmarking against industry best practices or competitors to understand relative positioning. Assessing maturity helps identify which

digital touch points need improvement, enhancing overall customer satisfaction and loyalty. A maturity assessment guides where to prioritize technology investments for the highest impact and return on investment. It highlights cultural or structural barriers to innovation, helping build a more agile and future-ready organization. Measuring DM uncovers gaps in technology adoption, digital skills, customer engagement, or integration of systems. For example, a hotel chain may realize it lacks mobile booking functionality or digital marketing skills, which puts it at a disadvantage. This study will help the organizations in the H&T industry in Sri Lanka to assess their digital capabilities, leadership capabilities, digital literacy of employers/employees, and digital maturity of the organizations. It will be a lighthouse for them to conduct their business effectively and efficiently.

The Sama Radial Indicator and 3D-Digital Maturity Model are recent developments. It was hard to find studies applying the newly developed models in real-life situations. This study tests the models with real-life data, fills a knowledge gap.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is focused on two parts.

2.1 Digital Maturity Models.

2.2 Sama Radial Indicator.

2.1 Digital Maturity Models

Westerman et al (2014) is the most applied model in assessing the DM of organizations. The 3-D Digital Maturity Model (3DDMM) of Konarasinghe (2025) is a recently developed model for measuring DM.

2.1.1 Westerman et al (2014) Model

Westerman's model evaluates organizations along two dimensions: digital capabilities and leadership capabilities. Digital Capabilities refers to the use of technology to change how the company operates. Leadership capabilities refer to the ability to drive transformation through vision, governance, and engagement. These two dimensions create a 2x2 matrix that classifies companies into four categories: Beginners, Fashionistas, Conservatives, and Digital Masters (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Four Levels of Digital Maturity (Source: Westerman et al., 2014)

Beginners have low digital capability and low leadership capability. They are often siloed or using legacy systems, they lack of strategic digital vision. Fashionistas have high digital capability and low leadership capability. They experiment with many digital tools but lack integration or governance. Their digital initiatives are often scattered or superficial. Conservatives have low digital capability but high leadership capability. They are cautious adopters of digital technology, focusing on control, risk mitigation, and efficiency. Digital Masters have high Digital Capability and high leadership capability. They combine strong technology with strong vision and governance. Efficient and agile operations, empowered employees, strong digital governance, and clear vision and change leadership are attributes of Digital Masters.

Westerman et al. (2014) define the median values of digital capabilities and leadership capabilities as the boundaries of the four categories of the matrix. However, median values are sample sensitive, hence, these boundaries change from sample to sample, changing the position of companies within the matrix. This is a clear problem of Westerman et al. (2014). Also, this model is unable to measure the value of DM of the organizations.

2.1.2 3-D Digital Maturity Model (3DDMM)

The 3DDMM of Konarasinghe (2025) defines three independent dimensions to the DM, they are: Digital Capabilities (X) of the organization, Leadership Capabilities (Y) of the organization, and the Digital Literacy (Z) of employers/ employees of the organization. The study assumes the DM of an organization as a function of the three variables: X, Y, and Z. By using the properties of vector space, the new DM conceptual framework is represented in 3-D vector space (Figure 2).

Figure 2: 3-D Digital Maturity Model (Source: Konarasinghe, 2025)

Model assumptions:

1. X , Y , and Z are real-valued functions.
2. $x, y, z \in R$ and $(x, y, z) \in R^3$
3. $x, y, z \geq 0$

Hence, DM of an organization = $\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$.

2.2 Sama Radial Indicator (SRI)

The SRI of Konarasinghe (2023) is a measurement scale developed to convert qualitative random variables to a continuous scale. The SRI is a semicircle (see Figure 3) that has three anchors: Totally Agree, Neutral, and Totally Disagree. The respondent will mark a point on the circumference of the circle as he/she feels how the response is close to one of the three anchors. The SRI measures the angle θ in the anticlockwise sense; the researcher obtains the arc length based on the angle. As the arc length is proportional to the angle, either the angle or the arc length could be used as the outcome of the respondent.

Figure 3: Sama Radial Indicator (Source: Konarasinghe, 2023)

In the usual notations, an arc with length S .

$$S = r\theta$$

Let, $r = 100$

Then, $S = 100\theta$

Item Response (S): $0 \leq S \leq 100\pi$

$$0 \leq S \leq 314.16$$

Where, S is a continuous random variable.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the study has three parts.

- 3.1 Questionnaire development and validation.
- 3.2 Modification to Sama Radial Indicator.
- 3.3 Sampling, data collection, and analysis.

3.1 Questionnaire Development and Validation

This study used the conceptual framework of Konarasinghe (2025) to measure the DM of organizations (see Figure 4). Accordingly, Digital Capability is measured through three dimensions: business strategy, technological expertise, and business models; Leadership Capability is measured through three dimensions: governance, change management, and culture; and Digital Literacy is measured through six dimensions: computer literacy, media literacy, information literacy, technology literacy, communication literacy and English literacy.

Figure 4: Conceptual Model of DM (Source: Konarasinghe, 2025)

This study developed a structured questionnaire to measure the random variables, and the development of the questionnaire was based on the item pools of Westerman et al. (2014), Rosmann (2018), and Son & Robb (2010). The Sama Radial Indicator was used to obtain the item responses. To test the validity of the questionnaire, a pre-test was conducted with the help of a sample of thirty academicians/researchers of Western Sydney University, Australia. The questionnaire validation was based on the Cronbach's Alpha test and the discussions with research experts. Table 1 gives a summary of the results of the Cronbach's Alpha test.

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha Test Results (Pre-Test)

Model	Number of items	Alpha value
Overall	14	0.956
Digital Capabilities	4	0.872
Leadership capabilities	4	0.725
Digital Literacy of Employer/Employee	6	0.924

Accordingly, Alpha value of the overall questionnaire (0.956) confirms that the reliability of the questionnaire is excellent. Also, Alpha values of variables: Digital Capabilities, leadership Capabilities, and Digital Literacy of employer/ employee show that the reliability of item responses is high ($\alpha > 0.7$).

3.2 Modification to Sama Radial Indicator

Based on the discussions with subject matter experts and general users, a slight adjustment was made to the Sama Radial Indicator of Konarasinghe (2023). It is such that Konarasinghe (2023) measured the angle in an anticlockwise sense (see Figure 3), but this study measures the angle in the clockwise sense (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Modified Sama Radial Indicator

The SRI is a semicircle; hence, the protractor image (without numbers) is used in the questionnaire to obtain item responses (see Figure 6). The numbers on the protractor are deleted to avoid respondents thinking about the scores.

Figure 6: Protractor without Numbers

The respondent was supposed to mark a point on the circumference as he/she felt how close to one of the three anchors: Completely Disagree, Neutral, and Completely Agree. This study defines the intervals as follows:

- $\theta = 0$: Completely Disagree
- $0 < \theta \leq 45$: Strongly Disagree
- $45 < \theta < 90$: Weakly Disagree
- $\theta = 90$: Neutral
- $90 < \theta < 135$: Weakly Agree
- $135 \leq \theta < 180$: Strongly Agree
- $\theta = 180$: Completely Agree

A Table of arc lengths (SRI Table) is developed to obtain an individual's item response value (see Appendix 1). Hence, the respondent has 180 response options. As the arc length is proportional to θ (the angle), either the arc length or the angle θ can be used as the measurement of the variable. This study uses the angle as the measurement.

3.3 Sampling, Data Collection, and Analysis

The Accommodation sector of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka is defined as the population of the study. It comprises three broad categories: Tourist hotels (A), Supplementary establishments (B), and other establishments (C). Category A includes classified tourist hotels, unclassified tourist hotels, boutique hotels/ boutique villas; Category B includes guest houses, rest houses, home stay units, tourist bungalows, rented tourist homes, rented tourist apartments and heritage bungalows/homes; Category C refers to those who are not formally registered with the Sri Lanka Tourism Development

Authority. Table 2 summarizes the types of accommodation establishments for the year 2020, data are not available for the unregistered establishments.

Table 2: Types of Accommodation Establishments in Sri Lanka (Source: SLTDA, 2020)

Type of Accommodation	Number of Establishments	Proportion
Classified Tourist hotels (1 star to 5 star)	484	15%
Unclassified Tourist hotels	246	7%
Boutique hotels/ Villas	82	2%
Supplementary establishments	2535	76%
Total	3347	

3.3.1 Sample Size Determination

Sample size determination is based on the standard statistical technique (Saunders & Levis, 2007; Greener, 2008; Sullivan, 2022).

$$n = p \cdot q \cdot \left(\frac{Z_{\alpha/2}}{e} \right)^2 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, n= Initial sample size, p = Proportion of respondents, q = 1-p, e =Error margin (5%),

α =Significance level (0.05)

The adjusted sample to the population size is; $n' = \frac{n}{1 + (n / N)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$

Where n' = Adjusted sample size, N= Population size

The non-response rate of the pre-test of the study is 2%. Hence, the minimum required sample of establishments is 30, but a random sample of 100 organizations was selected to increase the power of tests associated with data analysis.

The study's population is spread over the country; therefore, a multi-stage sampling technique was adopted (Saunders et al., 2007; Greener, 2008). The steps of multi-stage sampling are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Multi-stage Sampling of the Study

Stage	Sampling Technique	Method of sample selection	Description
1	Simple Random Sampling	A table of random numbers was used to select a random sample of 05 districts from the country's 25 districts.	i. Hambantota ii. Kalutara iii. Kandy iv. Gampaha v. Matara
2	Stratified sampling	Obtain a sample of different types of accommodation establishments, capturing star hotels to guest houses around each attraction	Sample size = 100 organizations
3	Cluster Sampling	Meet the owner or CEO of each organization and leave the questionnaires in the establishment's common area, requesting that employers/ employees fill them out.	Sample size: 100 employers/employees

3.3.2 Method of Data Collection

The data collection of the study was conducted in Sri Lanka from April to June 2024. The questionnaire was handed over to the owner/CEO of the organization, who requested to be placed in a common area so employees could obtain the questionnaire and complete it. It was expected that the questionnaire would take between 10 to 15 minutes to complete. Participants were given two days to complete the questionnaire. Participants were requested to deposit their completed questionnaires into a sealed box located conveniently on the premises. The researcher of the study was the only person with access to the sealed box. The CEO/owner had no access to the sealed box.

3.3.3 Methods of Data Analysis

The SRI converted the outcomes of the latent variables to a continuous scale; hence, the quantitative approach was used for the data analysis. The statistical software SPSS and Minitab were used for the data analysis. Cronbach's alpha test and Correlation Analysis were used for questionnaire validation. Anderson-Darling's Normality test was used to test the normality of random variables.

4. RESULTS

A graphical summary of the data was obtained to understand the behaviour of the variables: DC, LC, and DL_E.

4.1 Digital Capability (DC) of Organizations in the H&T Industry of Sri Lanka

Five items were used to measure the DC of an organization, and the average of the item responses was taken as 'DC'. Figure 7 is the Graphical summary of DC, it contains: the minimum and maximum value of the data set, mean, median and quartiles, histogram, boxplot, measurements of variation, skewness and kurtosis, 95% confidence interval for mean, median, and standard deviation, and the Anderson Darling normality test results.

Figure 7: Graphical summary of DC

DC ranges from 16 to 180, the mean is 107.22, the median is 108.30, the first quartile is 75.75, and the third quartile is 141.25. The 95% confidence interval of the mean and median overlap; hence, there is enough evidence to say that the mean and median are not significantly different. The Histogram is somewhat symmetrical; the box plot is symmetrical, as such, normality of the random variable 'DC' is assumed. The Anderson-Darling Normality test was used to test the following hypothesis.

H₀: Data are normally distributed

H₁: Data are not normally distributed

Theoretically, if the P-value of the test is less than the significance level, the null hypothesis can be rejected. In this instance, P-value (0.062) is greater than the significance level (0.05), therefore null hypothesis is not rejected, and the normality of the random variable 'DC' is confirmed. Accordingly, most of the organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka have a moderate level of digital capabilities, and few organizations have very high or very low digital capabilities. There is a 95% chance that the population mean lies in the interval (98.61, 115.84).

4.2 Leadership Capability (LC) of Organizations in the H&T Industry of Sri Lanka

Three items were used to measure the LC, and the average of the item responses was taken as LC. According to Figure 8, the LC ranges from 55 to 180, the mean is 124.39, and the median is 123.33. The 95% confidence interval of the mean and the median overlap; hence, there is enough evidence to say that the mean and median are not significantly different. The Histogram and the box plot do not suggest the symmetry of the dataset, but the Anderson-Darling normality test confirms that the random variable LC is normally distributed (P-value=0.053 > Significance level 0.05).

Figure 8: Graphical Summary of LC

There is a 95% chance that the population mean lies in the interval (117.58, 131.20); as such, most of the organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka have a moderate level of leadership capabilities, and few organizations have very high or very low leadership capabilities. However, the leadership capabilities of the organizations are higher than their digital capabilities.

4.3 Digital Literacy (DL_E) of Employers /Employees of the Organizations in the H&T Industry of Sri Lanka

Six items were used to measure the Digital Literacy of Employers /Employees (DL_E).

Figure 9: Graphical Summary of DL

As per Figure 9, DL_E ranges from 8.33 to 180; the data set contains extremely low values (outliers), the mean is 146.17, the median is 168.33, the first quartile is 128.08, and the third quartile is 180.00. The 95% confidence interval of the mean and the median overlap, but the histogram is not symmetrical. The Histogram and the box plot suggest that the dataset is negatively skewed and not symmetric. The Anderson-Darling normality test rejects the normality of the random variable DL (P-value < 0.005 < Significance level 0.05). The third quartile of the data set and the maximum value of the data are the same, which means the digital literacy of one-fourth of the respondents is extremely high, however, the outliers show that there were a few respondents with extremely low digital literacy. There is a 95% chance that the population median lies in the interval (151.67, 176.71), which also confirms the higher digital literacy of the employers/employees of the organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka. Among the three capabilities, the

organizations of the H&T industry of Sri Lanka have the highest capability in digital literacy of employers/ employees.

4.4 Digital Maturity (DM) of Organizations in the H&T Industry of Sri Lanka

The 3D-Digital Maturity Model (3DDMM) is used to calculate the DM of the organizations; it is such that

$$DM = \sqrt{DC^2 + LC^2 + DL_E^2} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

By the definition, the range of DM is from 0 to 311.77.

Figure 10: Graphical Summary of DM of Organizations in the H&T

The range of DM of the organizations is from 70.99 to 311.77, the mean value is 234.02, the first quartile is 202.94, the median is 246.53, the third quartile is 279.09, accordingly DM of: one-fourth of the organizations is below 202.94, one-fourth of the organizations is between 279.09 to 311.77 and rest of the organizations lies between 202.94 to 279.09. Indeed, the DM of the organizations is negatively skewed, with more organizations having higher DM. As per the results, the DM of the organizations in the H&T industry is high. (See Figure 10).

Results revealed that the random variables, DC and LC, are normally distributed. Even if the random variable DL_E is not normally distributed, the sampling distribution of DL_E is approximately normally distributed. Theoretically, the sum of squares of normal

distributions follows a Chi-Square distribution, hence, DM^2 follows a Chi-Square distribution, and the DM follows a Chi distribution with degree of freedom 3 (Johnson, Kotz, & Balakrishnan, 1994; Casella & Berger, 2002); that is,

$$DM = \sqrt{DC^2 + LC^2 + DL_E^2} \sim \chi_3.$$

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The digital transformation changes the horizons of the H&T industry across the world. Organizations in the H&T industry are forced to adopt digital technologies to meet the demands of customers and to survive in the highly competitive market. However, digitalization is a time-consuming and costly process, hence, organizations need to assess their position on digitalization. DM is the measurement to assess the degree of adoption of digital technologies. Sri Lanka is a famous travel destination. As a developing economy, H&T is highly important to the economy of country. Hence, this study is focused on measuring the DM of organizations in the H&T industry of Sri Lanka.

Literature revealed that the Westerman et al. (2014) model is the widely applied model in measuring the DM of organizations. Konarasinghe (2025) has identified theoretical gaps in Westerman et al. (2014) and developed a new model for measuring the DM. However, the newly developed model, named 3DDMM, has not been used to measure the DM; it is a practical knowledge gap. Hence, this study intended to use the 3DDMM for measuring DM. The 3DDMM uses three independent random variables to measure the DM; they are DC, LC, and DL_E . These variables are latent variables, not directly measured; hence, structured questionnaires are used to obtain the item responses and then calculate the values of the variables (Rosmann, 2018; Son & Rob, 2010). As per the literature, Likert scales are the most applied scales to measure the latent variables. Yet Konarasinghe (2025) defined DC, LC, and DL_E as real-valued continuous random variables. Hence, it is essential to convert these latent variables to a continuous scale. Literature revealed that Sama Radial Indicator (SRI) of Konarasinghe (2023) can convert qualitative random variables into a continuous scale, and the random variables become normally distributed. Yet the method has not been applied in real-life applications. This study used the SRI to measure DC, LC, and DL_E and found that DC and LC are normally distributed, but not DL_E . However, DL_E is a continuous random variable; by the Central Limit theorem, it can be assumed that DL_E is approximately normally distributed, provided the sample size is large (>30). The 3DDMM has successfully measured the DM of organizations. Results revealed that the DC and LC of the organizations in the H&T industry are moderate, but DL_E is high. The study showed that the DM follows a Chi distribution.

It is concluded that SRI is a suitable scale for converting qualitative random variables to a continuous scale, and 3DDMM is a suitable model for assessing the DM of the organizations. The SRI is applicable to any field of research; hence, it is recommended to use the method for measuring the qualitative random variables for further confirmation. Also, the 3DDMM is applicable for any industry; hence recommended to apply in

measuring the DM of organizations in other industries, as it will help the governments and policy developers to benchmark the DM.

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APPENDIX 1

Sama Radial Indicator (SRI) Table

Assume $r=100$

Angle (in Degrees)- θ^0	Angle (in Radians)- θ^c	Arc Length (S)
0	0.00000	0.000
1	0.01745	1.745
2	0.03491	3.491
3	0.05236	5.236
4	0.06981	6.981
5	0.08727	8.727
6	0.10472	10.472
7	0.12217	12.217
8	0.13963	13.963
9	0.15708	15.708
10	0.17453	17.453
11	0.19199	19.199

12	0.20944	20.944
13	0.22689	22.689
14	0.24435	24.435
15	0.26180	26.180
16	0.27925	27.925
17	0.29671	29.671
18	0.31416	31.416
19	0.33161	33.161
20	0.34907	34.907
21	0.36652	36.652
22	0.38397	38.397
23	0.40143	40.143
24	0.41888	41.888
25	0.43633	43.633
26	0.45379	45.379
27	0.47124	47.124
28	0.48869	48.869
29	0.50615	50.615
30	0.52360	52.360
31	0.54105	54.105
32	0.55851	55.851
33	0.57596	57.596
34	0.59341	59.341

35	0.61087	61.087
36	0.62832	62.832
37	0.64577	64.577
38	0.66323	66.323
39	0.68068	68.068
40	0.69813	69.813
41	0.71558	71.558
42	0.73304	73.304
43	0.75049	75.049
44	0.76794	76.794
45	0.78540	78.540
46	0.80285	80.285
47	0.82030	82.030
48	0.83776	83.776
49	0.85521	85.521
50	0.87266	87.266
51	0.89012	89.012
52	0.90757	90.757
53	0.92502	92.502
54	0.94248	94.248
55	0.95993	95.993
56	0.97738	97.738
57	0.99484	99.484

58	1.01229	101.229
59	1.02974	102.974
60	1.04720	104.720
61	1.06465	106.465
62	1.08210	108.210
63	1.09956	109.956
64	1.11701	111.701
65	1.13446	113.446
66	1.15192	115.192
67	1.16937	116.937
68	1.18682	118.682
69	1.20428	120.428
70	1.22173	122.173
71	1.23918	123.918
72	1.25664	125.664
73	1.27409	127.409
74	1.29154	129.154
75	1.30900	130.900
76	1.32645	132.645
77	1.34390	134.390
78	1.36136	136.136
79	1.37881	137.881
80	1.39626	139.626

81	1.41372	141.372
82	1.43117	143.117
83	1.44862	144.862
84	1.46608	146.608
85	1.48353	148.353
86	1.50098	150.098
87	1.51844	151.844
88	1.53589	153.589
89	1.55334	155.334
90	1.57080	157.080
91	1.58825	158.825
92	1.60570	160.570
93	1.62316	162.316
94	1.64061	164.061
95	1.65806	165.806
96	1.67552	167.552
97	1.69297	169.297
98	1.71042	171.042
99	1.72788	172.788
100	1.74533	174.533
101	1.76278	176.278
102	1.78024	178.024
103	1.79769	179.769

104	1.81514	181.514
105	1.83260	183.260
106	1.85005	185.005
107	1.86750	186.750
108	1.88496	188.496
109	1.90241	190.241
110	1.91986	191.986
111	1.93732	193.732
112	1.95477	195.477
113	1.97222	197.222
114	1.98968	198.968
115	2.00713	200.713
116	2.02458	202.458
117	2.04204	204.204
118	2.05949	205.949
119	2.07694	207.694
120	2.09440	209.440
121	2.11185	211.185
122	2.12930	212.930
123	2.14675	214.675
124	2.16421	216.421
125	2.18166	218.166
126	2.19911	219.911

127	2.21657	221.657
128	2.23402	223.402
129	2.25147	225.147
130	2.26893	226.893
131	2.28638	228.638
132	2.30383	230.383
133	2.32129	232.129
134	2.33874	233.874
135	2.35619	235.619
136	2.37365	237.365
137	2.39110	239.110
138	2.40855	240.855
139	2.42601	242.601
140	2.44346	244.346
141	2.46091	246.091
142	2.47837	247.837
143	2.49582	249.582
144	2.51327	251.327
145	2.53073	253.073
146	2.54818	254.818
147	2.56563	256.563
148	2.58309	258.309
149	2.60054	260.054

150	2.61799	261.799
151	2.63545	263.545
152	2.65290	265.290
153	2.67035	267.035
154	2.68781	268.781
155	2.70526	270.526
156	2.72271	272.271
157	2.74017	274.017
158	2.75762	275.762
159	2.77507	277.507
160	2.79253	279.253
161	2.80998	280.998
162	2.82743	282.743
163	2.84489	284.489
164	2.86234	286.234
165	2.87979	287.979
166	2.89725	289.725
167	2.91470	291.470
168	2.93215	293.215
169	2.94961	294.961
170	2.96706	296.706
171	2.98451	298.451
172	3.00197	300.197

173	3.01942	301.942
174	3.03687	303.687
175	3.05433	305.433
176	3.07178	307.178
177	3.08923	308.923
178	3.10669	310.669
179	3.12414	312.414
180	3.14159	314.159